

SUG'ORILADIGAN TIPIK BO'Z TUPROQLAR SHAROITIDA KUNGABOQAR NAVLARINING O'SISHI VA RIVOJLANISHI

J.Eshonqulov

Toshkent davlat agrar universiteti dotsenti

Q.Rashidov

Toshkent davlat agrar universiteti 3-bosqich talabasi

E.Ravshanov

Toshkent davlat agrar universiteti 3-bosqich talabasi

1992.jamoliddin@mail.ru

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada Toshkent viloyatining sug'oriladigan tipik bo'z tuproqlari sharoitida kuzgi bug'doydan so'ng takroriy ekin sifatida parvarishlangan kungaboqarning sug'orish tartiblari va rivojlanish fazalari bo'yicha ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

***Kalit so'zlar:** Kungaboqar, o'sish, rivojlanish, takroriy ekin, sug'orish tartiblari, hosildorlik.*

ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the procedures and stages of development of sunflowers irrigation, which was bred as a repeated crop after autumn wheat in the conditions of irrigated typical peat soils of the Tashkent region.

***Key words:** Sunflower, growth, development, repeated cultivation, irrigation procedures, productivity.*

KIRISH: Aholisining sonining ortishi oziq-ovqat jumladan, o'simlik moyi va oqsilli mahsulotlarga bo'lgan talab kun sayin ortib bormoqda. O'simlik moyi ishlab chiqarish sanoatida soya va kungaboqar asosiy xomashyo manbai bo'lib hisoblanadi. «Bugungi kunda yer yuzida 122,1 mln. gektar maydonda soya va 25,6 mln. gektar maydonda kungaboqar asosiy va takroriy muddatlarda yetishtirilmoqda. Dunyo mamlakatlarida bugungi kunda agrar sohada ekinlarni yetishtirishda suv tanqisligi muammosi kundan kunga ortib bormoqda. Moyli ekinlar yetishtiruvchi mamlakatlarda

hosildorlikni oshirish, sifatini yaxshilashda sug'orish muddatlari va me'yorlarini to'g'ri belgilash muhim hisoblanadi.

Moyli ekinlardan kungaboqar navlarini sug'orish me'yorlari va muddatlarini tuproq-iqlim sharoitlarini hisobga olgan holda to'g'ri belgilash, hosilining sifati va miqdoriga o'zining ijobiy ta'sirini ko'rsatadi. Hozirgi paytda dunyo aholisini o'simlik moyiga bo'lgan talabini qondirish, oziq-ovqat havfsizligini ta'minlashda takroriy ekiladigan soya va kungaboqarni sug'orishda maqbul sug'orish tartibi va suv iste'molini aniqlash bo'yicha tadqiqotlar olib borish dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Muammoning o'rganilganlik darajasi. Moyli ekinlardan soya va kungaboqarni asosiy va takroriy muddatlarda yetishtirish hamda ularning biologiyasi va yetishtirish agrotexnologiyalarini o'rganish bo'yicha xorijda P.Vavilov, A.Babich, G.Посыпанов, L.Vislobokova, O.Ivanova, S.Ivanov, L.Gubanov, V.Litvinov., A. Sevost'yanov, M.Miroshnichenko, S.Antonov, Ye.Yefimov, A.Nel, H.Loubser, P.Hammes, mamlakatimizda soya bo'yicha Q.Mirzajonov, X.Atabaeva, D.Yormatova, U.Norqulov, N.Xalilov, B.Xalikov, S.Isaev, I.Israilov, N.O'razmatov, F.Namozov, U.Ne'matov, X.Raxmonov, M.Mannopova, M.Sattorov, A.Iminov, A.Duysenov, A.Panjiev, O.Sottorov, moyli kungaboqar bo'yicha esa I.Anarboev, I.Ernazarov, **M.Lukov**, S.Tog'aeva kabi olimlar tomonidan keng qamrovli ilmiy ishlar olib borilgan. Shuning uchun kungaboqar o'simligini kuzgi bug'doydan so'ng takroriy ekin sifatida parvarishlashning maqbul sug'orish tartibini ishlab chiqish dolzarb vazifa hisoblanadi.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI.

Tajriba olib borilgan izlanishlar natijasiga ko'ra, kungaboqarning "Navruz" navi o'zini ancha ertapisharligini namoyon etdi. Bunda ushbu navni ChDNSga nisbatan 65–65–60 % namlikda tuproqning 0–50 sm hisobiy qatlami bo'yicha sug'orishda eng erta pishar bo'lib, 85 kunnni, sug'orish tartibiga mos lekin 0–70 sm hisobiy qatlam o'yicha 87 kunnni tashkil qilganligi tajribada kuzatildi. Sug'orish tartibi 75–75–65 % namlikda va sug'orish oldi tuproq namligi mos ravishda amalga oshirilgan varintda o'simlikning vegetatsiya davri 89 kundan iborat bo'ldi. Tajribada nazorat sifatida ekilgan kungaboqarning "Jaxongir" navi "Navro'z" naviga nisbatan kechpishar bo'lib, vegetatsiya davri 3 yilda o'rtacha 92 kungacha davom etdi yoki 7 kun kech pishishi kuzatildi. (1-jadvalda keltirilgan).

1-jadval

Kungaboqarning o'sishi va rivojlanishi dinamikasi sm, 2018 yil

V a r	Navlar	Tuproq sug'orish oldi namlik, ChDNS ga nis. %	Kungaboqarning bo'yi, sm			Barglar soni, dona			Savatcha- ning Diametri, sm., 1.10.
			1.08	1.09	1.10	1.08	1.09	1.10	
1	Jahongir	70-70-60	59,0	172,6	176,6	7,02	19,01	20,7	20,7
2	Navro'z	65-65-60	49,5	165,1	168,9	11,7	21,04	18,6	21,6
3		75-75-65	51,0	168,8	169,1	9,78	18,44	19,0	20,9
4		65-65-60	48,6	164,7	166,7	10,5	18,76	19,6	21,4
5		75-75-65	59,6	165,9	172,7	9,97	19,13	19,4	21,1

Sug'oriladigan tipik bo'z tuproqlarda parvarishlangan kungaboqarning navlarining o'sishi, rivojlanishi mavsum davomida turlicha bo'ldi. O'rtacha o'simlik bo'yi vegetatsiya ohiriga borib, eng yuqori ko'rsatkich "Jaxongir" navida uch yilda o'rtacha 176,6-184,4 sm eng past ko'rsatkich esa "Navruz" navi 65-65-60 % namlikda kuzatilib, o'rtacha 159,6-174 sm bo'ldi. Bu navning ChDNSga nisbatan 75-75-65 % namlik bo'yicha sug'orishda tuproqni 0-70 sm hisobiy qatlamida 172,7-181,6 santimetrni tashkil qildi. Fenologik kuzatishda o'lchov natijalariga ko'ra savatchaning diametri bo'yicha eng yuqori ko'rsatkich "Navro'z" navida ChDNSga nisbatan 65-65-60 % sug'orish tartibida va tuproqni namlash hisobiy qatlami 0-50 sm bo'lganda aniqlandi va 21,6-24,5 sm, barglar soni esa 21,4 donani tashkil etdi.

Tajribaning tuproqning 0-70 sm qatlami sug'orish oldi tuproq namligi 65-65-60 % namlik bo'yicha tuproqning hisobiy qatlami 0-70 smda sug'orish amalga oshirilganda kungaboqarning bo'y balandligi oktabr oyinin dastlabki o'n kunligida "Navro'z" navida 166,7 sm bo'ldi va barglar soni 19,6 donani tashkil etdi. Tajribaning 5-variantida 75-75-65 % namlikda tuproq namligiga 0-70 sm bo'lganda o'simlikning bo'y balandligi 176,6 sm bo'lsa, barglar soni esa 20,7 dona bo'lganligi kuzatildi

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